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Quantum Software Ante Portas: How to Prepare for a New Computing Paradigm?

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Quantum computing has received considerable interest in recent years due to its potential to solve computational problems that are intractable for even the best classical supercomputers. Significant progress has been achieved not only at the hardware level [1], but also at the software level with the emergence of cloud-based services for quantum computers, dedicated simulators, and quantum programming languages [2]. The ability to execute software on a quantum computer, however, is not enough to drive innovation. Similar to the state of classical computing during the software crisis in the 1960s [3], in order to extend beyond the proof-of-concept and achieve industry adoption, we require new tools, processes, and programming languages for quantum computing, and all in all, a new generation of (quantum) software engineers. In this article, we seek to provide an overview of where we stand and where we need to go to prepare for this new computing paradigm.

The potential of quantum computing lies in its fundamentally different approach to information processing. While a classical computer operates in one of 2^N states at any given time (where N is the number of available bits), a quantum computer can represent a probability distribution across 2^N states simultaneously through the phenomenon of superposition. Quantum parallelism (the ability to operate on all of these states at once), combined with entanglement (the correlation between probability distributions of quantum bits, or qubits), brought forth quantum algorithms. They often achieve up to exponential speed-ups over their classical counterparts for specific problem classes (see [4] and [5] for well-known examples).

Realising this potential, however, is far from trivial [6,7].

The current state of the field – often referred to as the Noisy Intermediate-Scale Quantum (NISQ) era [8] – is characterised by systems with 50–1000 physical qubits that are error-prone, have short coherence times, and lack full error correction. These hardware constraints shape how quantum software must be engineered. In the NISQ era, quantum software must be carefully optimised for circuit depth, gate count, and hardware-specific compilation strategies. Furthermore, the quantum computing landscape is heterogeneous [2], with multiple competing hardware platforms based on different physical implementations, each with distinct operational characteristics, gate sets, and connectivity topologies. This hardware diversity creates significant challenges for software portability and increases the need for abstraction layers that can shield software engineers from low-level hardware details while still enabling performance optimisation.

Besides limitations directly induced by the hardware, applications increasingly demand hybrid classical-quantum architectures where quantum processing units serve as specialised co-processors within larger computational workflows [9]. Major technology providers, such as IBM, Microsoft, Google, and AWS, are extensively investing in quantum cloud infrastructures and development frameworks, recognising that accessible software tooling will be critical for widespread adoption of the technology. Still, current quantum programming mostly occurs at the quantum circuit level [10], an abstraction

comparable to assembly languages for classical computers. Despite significant progress in the required tools and languages, significant gaps remain in areas such as debugging, testing, verification, and integrated development environments [11]. In addition, software engineering research has achieved several abstraction layers for classical computing that bridge the gap between human-oriented programs and machine-oriented representations. This achievement has not yet been made for quantum software.

Manuel Wimmer presents a keynote on "Integrating Quantum Technologies into European Informatics Departments" at ECSS 2025.

The quantum software engineering community is actively working to tackle these challenges by developing new or adapting existing methodologies from classical software engineering. For instance, we are working on model-driven engineering approaches that provide higher-level abstractions, e.g., for circuit composition [12], and search-based engineering approaches for automatically synthesising or optimising quantum circuits for specific objectives [13]. Adopting such established engineering methodologies for quantum software is a major challenge, as it requires a new generation of quantum software researchers capable of working at the intersection of quantum physics, computer science, and potential application domains.

This brings us to the next major challenge: education. An ad-hoc search of global quantum computing programmes reveals a heterogeneous landscape of over 100 study programmes worldwide, predominantly at the Master's level and typically building upon either computer

science or physics foundations. Industry partners such as IBM, Microsoft, Google, and AWS frequently collaborate with these programmes, which generally include quantum programming but rarely embed more advanced software engineering topics within broader quantum computing curricula. Notable exceptions include programmes at institutions such as KAISTⁱ, SDUⁱⁱ, and UTSⁱⁱⁱ that offer dedicated software engineering specialisations. However, a shared understanding of how to design comprehensive quantum software engineering curricula remains elusive. The European Commission's Quantum Europe Strategy^{iv} explicitly identifies this gap, noting that shortages are "*most critical in applied fields, including quantum software engineering, system integration, and quantum cybersecurity, slowing the commercialisation path for EU-based start-ups and scale-ups.*" Building a diverse, world-leading workforce through coordinated education, training, and talent mobility across the EU is a strategic priority that will require sustainable investment and curricular innovation. Bridging the skill gap demands not only technical training in quantum physics and programming, but also interdisciplinary collaboration capabilities, systems thinking, and software engineering skills—competencies that traditional physics or more theoretical computer science programmes often only cover to a limited extent.

As quantum computing technology continues to mature along ambitious roadmaps^v, the need for high-quality quantum software and comprehensive engineering methods will only intensify. Successfully navigating the transition from current NISQ devices to fault-tolerant quantum computers will require advances across the entire software stack: from circuit synthesis and optimisation algorithms, through compiler technologies and runtime systems, to high-level programming abstractions and integrated development tools. Moreover, questions of how quantum components integrate into larger software systems, how development practices scale from current 10–100 qubit systems to future 1000+ qubit systems, and what organisational

changes are necessary within software teams remain largely unexplored. The innovations that will ultimately drive quantum computing's impact will be enabled by quantum software, making it

essential that the computer science community tackles these challenges now, while the field is still taking shape.

ⁱ <https://quantum.kaist.ac.kr/english/main>

ⁱⁱ <https://www.uts.edu.au/research/centre-quantum-software-and-information>

ⁱⁱⁱ <https://www.sdu.dk/en/uddannelse/kandidat/quantum-computing>

^{iv} <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/quantum>

^v See, for example, IBM's projection to achieve thousands of logical qubits by the end of the decade: <https://www.ibm.com/quantum/technology> - other major technology providers estimate similar numbers.

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